

EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND COMPRESSION ON ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CNT-PEEK COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The effects of temperature and compression on the electrical conductivity of Poly Ether Ether Ketone (PEEK) filled with multi-walled carbon nanotube are investigated. Melt mixing was used to prepare the samples. The results show that increases in temperature (below T_g) and compression pressure result in increase in electrical conductivity.

Keywords: Compression Pressure, Carbon nanotubes, electrical conductivity, micro structure.

ABSTRACT

The novel properties and multifunctionality (such as electrical conductivity) of carbon nano tubes have stimulated tremendous interest in the development of nanotube reinforced polymer composites. The electrical conductivity of the nanotube filled PEEK composites is due to continuous conductive network formed in a specific arrangement by the nanotubes. An experimental investigation of electrical conductivity of nano composites consisting of CVD-grown multi-walled Carbon Nanotube and Poly Ether Ether Ketone is presented in this paper. Three different weight percentages of carbon nano tubes were dispersed with PEEK through intense shear mixing by calendaring technique in Brabender at 380°C. The resulting nanocomposites were processed into round shaped pieces of 25.4 mm diameter and 1.5 mm thickness. The samples are then simultaneously compressed by applying a pressure from zero to 40 MPa with an interval of 2 MPa and heated from 40°C to 140°C at an interval of 10°C. It has been found that electrical conductivity increases significantly with the application of heat and pressure. The results are graphically represented and supported by SEM images of the sample before and after applying pressure and temperature.

1. INTRODUCTION

Because of their nano-scale dimensions, exceptionally high electrical and thermal conductivities, low density, high tensile strength and Young's modulus, Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNT) have attracted considerable attention from both academic and technological areas to be an excellent choice of filler material for polymeric composites [1]. Since polymeric composites are multi-phase systems, their properties

can be tailored by modification of the polymer and their ratio of components. Apart from the conventional application of semiconducting materials for dissipation of static electricity, enhancement of electrical conductivity of polymer by mixing them with multiwalled carbon nanotubes has found significant applications in newer areas such as electronic equipment, pressure sensitive switches, important strategic materials such as Electromagnetic Interference (EMI)/Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) shielding in computer and cellular phone housing, floor heating elements etc. Smart materials can identify a change in the environment and respond to it by performing both sensing and actuation. The usual stimuli are pressure, temperature, electricity, vibration, etc. whereas the useful responses are changes of conductivity, heating, mechanical/acoustic damping etc. [2].

K.P. Sau and his co-workers [3] measured the electrical conductivity of carbon fiber filled composites based on nitrile rubber, EPDM and their blend to check the percolation limit for each system. N.C. Das et al [4] investigated the effect of processing parameters like mixing time, rotor speed, mixing temperature, vulcanization time and pressure and service conditions like applied pressure and temperature on the electrical resistivity of rubber based composites. They used carbon black and short carbon fiber (SCF) as the filler material in their investigation. Influence of unidirectional pressure on the electrical conductivity of carbon black filled polyethylene was examined by Wang Ke and his team members [5]. Recently Giang T.Pham and his group [6] worked on development of strain sensors using MWCNT and thermoplastic matrix PMMA. They found a wide range of sensitivity which is comparable to the conventional resistance-type strain gauges.

In the present article, the variation of electrical resistance of advanced thermoplastic composites made of MWCNT and PEEK for different CNT loadings with temperature and high compression pressure are investigated. The change of electrical resistance of the composites with pressure and temperature depends on the polymer characteristics such as crystallinity, molecular weight, and aggregate structure, on structures of CNT fillers and on the interaction between the polymer and the filler. Analytical theories such as percolation, conduction network theory, tunnel effect mechanism and electric emission theory are proposed in the literature to explain the phenomenon [7]. A simple model based on compression pressure is developed in this article to explain the change in the electrical resistance with the application of pressure.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Poly (ether ether ketone) powder of grain size 80 μ purchased from Good Fellow, England was used as polymer matrix and Multiwalled Carbon Nano-Tube (MWCNT) Bay tubes C150P (C-purity \geq 95 wt.%, length $>$ 1 μ m, diameter 4–13 nm, synthesized by chemical vapor deposition) purchased from Bayer Material Science, Germany was used as the filler in this study to fabricate the samples. The physical properties of MWCNT and PEEK powder are presented in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 1: Physical properties of PEEK

Density(kg/m ³)	1263
Specific heat capacity (J/kg.K)	1339
Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	0.251
Powder size (micron)	80

Table 2: Physical Properties of MWCNT

Young's Modulus (TPa)	~ 1-1.2
Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	> 300
Electrical resistivity (Ω -m)	10 ⁻⁶
Bulk density (kg/m ³)	~140

2.2 Sample Preparation

The melting and high temperature shear mixing was done in a laboratory scale Torque Rheometry system Brabender Intelli-Torque Plasti-Corder (type IT 7150) at mixing temperature of 380°C, rotor speed 100 rpm and mixing time 20 minutes. The CNT/PEEK melt is again processed in Wabash compression molding machine at 340°C with compaction pressure of 10 tons and holding time 15 minutes using a special stainless steel mold. This produces 6 round shaped samples at a time having 25.4 mm diameter and 1.5 mm thickness. After cooling and solidification, the samples are obtained, polished and tested for electrical characterization. Different weight percentages of CNT starting from 3% were mixed with PEEK. At low percentages of CNT, even though the material is conductive, there is significant variation in conductivity. Several attempts were made to find the minimum weight percentage of CNT at which the sample variation of electrical conductivity is minimum. When the desired level of conductivity with minimum fluctuations among the samples is obtained, the samples were again processed in a Wabash hot press at 340°C with a very little compaction pressure of ½ ton to impregnate the conductive copper mesh on both surfaces. The copper meshes are used for connection to electrical wires for electrical conduction measurement. Electrical measurement is done while compression pressure is applied using MTS Testing machine.

2.3 Sample Testing

The volumetric resistivity of the composites with resistivity $\geq 10^8 \Omega$ -cm was measured using an Agilent high resistance meter (Model 4339B). To determine the volumetric resistivity at elevated temperatures, the entire electrode system was placed in a confined aluminium heater where the temperature could be monitored and controlled over the range 20°C- 500°C. Heat was supplied to the heating surfaces of the heater as well as to the sample by a programmable i-series Temperature/Process controller from Omega Engineering Inc. USA. The heater was covered with insulating material to prevent heat loss to the surroundings by convection heat transfer. The samples are then compressed by applying a pressure from zero to 40 MPa with an interval of 2 MPa. Temperature is applied simultaneously at room temperature and at elevated temperatures from 40°C to 140°C at an interval of 10°C. The sample resistance was measured across the thickness of the sample by using a FLUKE digital multimeter, which can measure resistances up to 100 M Ω .

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Electrical conductivity of thermoplastic composites is due to the formation of a continuous conductive network in the polymer matrix [3]. This network consists of specific spatial arrangement of conductive elements so that low resistance electrical paths are developed for free movement of electrons.

3.1 Determination of Critical Amount of CNT in PEEK Matrix

Figure 1 shows the variation of electrical conductivity with different weight percentages of CNT from 6% to 10% mixed with PEEK. At the same mixing conditions, as the amount of CNT was increased, average deviation of magnitude of electrical conductivity from the mean value was found to be decreasing. Typical values of standard deviation of electrical conductivity of randomly selected samples were 95% for 6% CNT, 76% for 7% CNT, 37% for 8% CNT, 26.6% for 9% CNT and 16% for 10% CNT. Further increase of amount of CNT may lead to the formation of agglomerates and hence the following investigation was carried out for the samples containing CNT of 8% to 10%.

Figure 1: Variation of Electrical Conductivity of CNT-PEEK composites for different weight% of CNT @ 1.0 V set voltage

3.1 Effect of Temperature

The effect of temperature on electrical conductivity of polymer composites is quite complex. Various factors affect the variation of conductivity against temperature. The temperature coefficient of resistance may be positive (PCT), negative (NCT) or zero, depending upon the concentration of filler and the nature of the polymers and the filler. As shown in the figure 2, a negative temperature coefficient of resistivity (NCT effect) has been noticed in the case of CNT-PEEK composites, i.e. electrical resistance of CNT-filled PEEK composite progressively decreases with the increase of temperature

up to the highest temperature of 140°C in these experiments. This behavior can be explained in terms of three main theories, i.e. conduction by network formation, tunneling and electric field radiation [4]. Differential thermal expansion of the CNT aggregate and polymer matrix, formation of further conductive networks during heating because of flocculation of CNT are primarily responsible for this behavior. Electron emission at high temperature between two consecutive CNT aggregates separated by a small gap, aerial oxidation leading to the formation of polar groups are two other reasons for improvement of electrical conductivity.

According to the hopping or tunneling mechanism of charged particles (i.e. electrons) in the system, with increasing temperature, the gap between two CNTs decreases because of uneven thermal expansion coefficient of CNT and PEEK. Accordingly, the probability of tunneling of electrons increases which is reflected in the significant increase of conductivity with temperature. With the gradual increase of CNT loading, the presence of large number of CNT contacts ensures a much higher probability of tunneling.

Figure 2: Comparison of electrical resistance at different temperatures without any pressure

Fig 3a. SEM micro-graph of 9%CNT-PEEK composites before test

Fig 3b. SEM micro-graph of 9%CNT-PEEK composites after test

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images of 9%CNT-PEEK composites are shown in figure 3 before and after the test. Excellent dispersion and homogeneous distribution of MWCNTs in the composite were obtained because of high temperature shear mixing in Brabender for a considerable amount of time. Before the test as shown in figure 3a, there is sufficient inter-particle gap. Upon applying pressure and temperature, this inter-particle distance is significantly reduced making CNTs closely connected each other as observed in figure 3b, which ultimately leads to the formation of a good conductive network.

3.2 Effect of Pressure

Variation of electrical conductivity of samples containing three different weight percentage of CNT-PEEK composites at different pressures are shown in figure 4. The resistance data reported here are the average of three samples and are reproducible within 2%. Electrical conductivity increases with increasing applied pressure up to a certain level.

Figure 4(a): At room temperature

Figure 4(b): At 40°C

Figure 4(c): At 50°C

Figure 4(d): At 60°C

Figure 4: Electrical resistance vs. applied pressure at different temperatures

It can be considered that two processes play an important role on the electrical conductivity at the same time when pressure is applied: One is the gap among the CNT aggregates that becomes smaller due to compression and the other is the conductive pathways which are reestablished due to the orientation of the plane. The electrical conductivity should be determined by the net result of these two processes. When the pressure is completely removed, the conductive pathways are temporarily interrupted and the conductivity of the samples decreases even beyond the initial value at no pressure. Relaxation of CNT also has effect in this process. However since PEEK is considerably stiff material, this relaxation is not very significant at temperatures considered.

3.3 Semi-Empirical Model to Explain Electrical Properties

A simple mathematical model has been developed to correlate the experimental data of electrical resistance under the effect of compression. Let us consider a small sample of initial thickness t and cross sectional area A . At two different pressures P_i and P_f , the electrical resistance are given by

$$R_i = \frac{\rho_i t_i}{A} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$R_f = \frac{\rho_f t_f}{A} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

where ρ_i and ρ_f are the resistivity and t_i and t_f are the thicknesses of the sample at two pressures P_i and P_f .

Dividing equation (2) by equation (1),

$$\frac{R_f}{R_i} = \frac{\rho_f t_f}{\rho_i t_i} = \frac{\rho_f (t + \epsilon_f t)}{\rho_i (t + \epsilon_i t)} = \frac{\rho_f (1 + \epsilon_f)}{\rho_i (1 + \epsilon_i)} = \frac{\rho_f \left(1 + \frac{\sigma_f}{E}\right)}{\rho_i \left(1 + \frac{\sigma_i}{E}\right)} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Since the resistivity ρ is not strongly dependent on pressure, to simplify the analysis, for the same temperature, we assume this material property constant.

After simplification, $R_f = R_i \frac{E + \sigma_f}{E + \sigma_i} \dots\dots\dots (4)$

In this equation, σ 's are calculated at different pressures by using $\sigma = \frac{\text{Compression Force}}{x\text{-sectional area}}$ and Modulus of Elasticity, E was taken from the results of Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) carried out from room temperature to 250°C as shown in figure 5. Typical value of E at room temperature as obtained from this analysis is 3149 MPa.

Fig 5: Dynamic-Mechanical Analysis (DMA) of 9% CNT-PEEK Composites

Electrical resistance (in ohm) obtained at room temperature with respect to applied pressure (in MPa) for 9% CNT-PEEK sample is plotted in figure 6. The results obtained by the simple model are in good agreement with those obtained by experiment.

Figure 6: Comparison of electrical resistance of 9% CNT-PEEK composites at room temperature obtained by experiment and the proposed model.

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